

Exploring How Online Consumer-Generated Advertising Impacts Purchase Intention in C2C Marketplace of Education Sector

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ABSTRACT

Private tuitions and coaching classes have been integral part of Indian education system for long. Earlier, private tutors used to promote their courses through consumer-generated advertisements (CGA) via different offline modes especially through newspapers, posters on walls, leaflets etc. Since pandemic, online promotion of private tuitions and coaching classes through CGA in C2C marketplace especially on social media platforms is playing very effective role to generate 'purchase intention' and pull consumers. Mode of instruction could be offline or online. The digital revolution spotlights 'purchase intention', closely linked to online CGA in C2C marketplaces. Trust in user-generated content, peer influence, quality assurance, and personalization shape it. To thrive in the digital promotion and education landscape, private tutorials and coaching centres need adaptable marketing strategies, improved quality, community engagement, partnerships, and data analytics. Trust on consumer-generated advertising, reviews and ratings, usefulness, heavily influence purchase intention to attract consumers in education sector. Peer influence, grounded in social proof theory, guides choices, affecting purchase decisions. Consumer-generated advertising serves as quality assurance, drawing and reassuring students evaluating educational offerings and usefulness. Algorithms customize recommendations, boosting engagement and purchase intention. Novelty of the work is largely in terms of giving new direction to managerial practice. The understanding and appreciation of the influencers will lead to better performance in present market trend with structural change of the industry. The managerial implication, consumer implication, overall marketing implication of the new avatars of online marketing in service sector contribute towards uniqueness of the study.

Keywords: Purchase Intention, Consumer-Generated Advertising (CGA), Communication, Private Tutors, Coaching classes

A. Introduction

In the era of the digital revolution, education, much like other sectors, has experienced a profound transformation in how people interact with its services. This shift is particularly noticeable in the realm of online Consumer-to-Consumer (C2C) marketplaces, where educational materials, courses, and mentorship services are exchanged. In this dynamic environment, the concept of 'purchase intention' plays a crucial role. Purchase intention, representing a consumer's willingness to acquire a product or service, is deeply intertwined with online consumer-generated advertising (CGA), which is integral to C2C marketplaces in education.

First and foremost, trust and authenticity are paramount. In the pursuit of educational offerings, consumers now place their trust in consumer-generated advertising, including reviews and ratings. These reviews serve as a reliable benchmark for assessing the credibility and quality of educational products. Positive feedback from fellow learners becomes a beacon of trust, significantly influencing purchase intention.

Furthermore, the power of peer influence, a concept deeply rooted in social psychology and highlighted by Cialdini (1984), plays a pivotal role. Aspiring scholars and learners often make choices based on the actions and opinions of their peers within the C2C marketplace community. Seeing fellow learners actively engaging with or endorsing educational resources can strongly sway their purchasing decisions.

Quality assurance is another crucial factor tied to purchase intention. Positive consumer-generated advertising serves as a robust assurance of the high quality of educational offerings. Reviews and ratings, emblematic of consumer-generated advertising, provide potential learners with valuable insights into the perceived quality of courses, tutors, or educational materials. Elevated ratings and enthusiastic recommendations inevitably boost purchase intention.

Lastly, personalization cannot be underestimated. Algorithms, with their ability to analyze user behaviour and preferences, offer personalized recommendations. This tailored approach aligns educational offerings with individual learners' preferences, significantly boosting purchase intention.

As these multifaceted factors converge to shape purchase intention, they, in turn, have profound implications for private tutors and coaching classes. Firstly, private tutors must carefully craft their marketing strategies. Active promotion through consumer-generated advertising, fostering positive reviews, and skilfully managing negative feedback are essential. Building and maintaining an online reputation plays a critical role, as it directly influences purchase intention.

At the same time, improving ‘educational quality’ and updating the ‘mode of instruction especially through online’ become a strategic imperative. To elevate purchase intention, private tutors and coaching centres must dedicate themselves to enhance the educational experience continually. Consumer-generated advertising being interactive serves as a perpetual feedback channel, highlighting areas in need of improvement. Being responsive to this feedback loop is vital for continuously enhancing educational offerings.

In addition, private tutors and coaching centres can actively engage in community building within C2C marketplaces and social media. Cultivating community participation amplifies the influence of peer recommendations and social proof. Establishing brand communities, as proposed by Muniz and O’Guinn (2001), fosters a sense of shared experiences, bolstering each other’s purchase intentions.

Moreover, opportunities for partnerships and influencer marketing emerge as potent avenues. Collaborating with influential figures within C2C social media platforms can enhance visibility and credibility. When endorsed by influential individuals, such alliances have a profound impact on purchase intention.

Finally, private tutors and coaching classes should harness the power of data through analytics. Within this wealth of data lies valuable insights into user behaviour and preferences. Equipped with this data-driven knowledge, private tutorials can fine-tune their marketing strategies and offer customized recommendations, wielding significant influence over purchase intention.

In summary, exploring purchase intention in the context of online consumer-generated advertising (CGA) within C2C marketplaces, especially in education, reveals a complex interplay of trust, peer influence, quality assurance, and personalization. Private tutorials must adapt and refine their marketing strategies, effectively apply consumer-generated advertising, prioritize educational quality, foster community engagement, explore strategic alliances, and leverage data analytics to thrive in the ever-evolving educational marketplace shaped by the digital revolution. Understanding and guiding purchase intention remains a pivotal factor for private tutors and coaching centres aspiring to succeed in this dynamic educational landscape.

B. Literature Review

Consumer engagement within the domain of online consumer-generated advertising (CGA) in Consumer-to-Consumer (C2C) marketplaces has recently emerged as a compelling research area, particularly in the context of the education sector. This section presents a comprehensive literature review, focusing on purchase intention and its key determinants within this framework.

Online Consumer-Generated Advertising in C2C Marketplace

Due to the significant increase in smartphone usage, consumer-generated advertising (CGA) on online platforms has grown in popularity across different sectors with a special focus on the education sector. The idea of consumer-generated advertising (CGA) in a customer-to-customer (C2C) marketplace has a critical role to play for private tutors and coaching classes to develop their market in a quickly expanding digital environment. CGA is defined as "any publicly distributed, consumer-generated advertising message whose subject is a collectively recognized brand/product" by Berthon (2008). The current study expands the meaning of CGA and conceptualizes it from the perspective of a consumer who uses the C2C market to make money for themselves without necessarily having a B2C organizational structure or strategy. One branch of consumer-generated advertising (CGA) is customer-to-customer (C2C) classified ads, which are 'short' advertisements in print, electronic, radio, and digital media. Online CGA on social media platforms for such unorganized businesses more from a small office/home office (SOHO), draw advertisement reaction from consumers. CGA performs noticeably better in acquiring consumer trust and thereby engaging customers more (Ertimur, 2011; Knoll, 2016; Lawrence, 2013) as compared to other internet advertising tactics. Since CGA is viewed as a more authentic, credible, recognized, engaging, and non-corporate consumer source, it enjoys high levels of trust (Lawrence, 2013). According to Roesler (2017), about 90% of buyers base their purchasing decisions on user-generated content. In the education sector, online CGA can be easily adopted by private tutors and coaching classes to attract consumers.

Purchase Intention and Trust

Trust is a foundational factor influencing purchase intention through consumer-generated advertising in online C2C marketplaces. Research by Dellarocas, Zhang, and Awad (2007) emphasizes the significant role of trust in user-generated content such as reviews and ratings. In the education sector, where prospective students seek reliable information about courses and tutorials, trust in peer-generated reviews becomes crucial (Smith & Wheeler, 2002).

Peer Influence and Social Proof

The concept of social proof, popularized by Cialdini (1984), asserts that individuals tend to follow the actions and decisions of others when making choices. In online C2C marketplaces, potential students are more likely to engage with educational offerings that have garnered positive attention from their peers (Zhu & Zhang, 2010). Peer influence and social proof thus significantly impact purchase intention in the education sector.

Quality Assurance through Consumer-generated Advertising

Consumer-generating advertising, user-generated content, including reviews and ratings, serves as a quality assurance mechanism. Positive reviews not only attract more consumers but also offer assurance of the educational product or service's quality (Chevalier & Mayzlin, 2006). In the context of education, this is vital for prospective students evaluating courses and tutors.

Personalization and Tailored Recommendations

Personalization in online consumer-generated advertising in context of C2C marketplaces is facilitated by algorithms that analyse user behaviour and preferences. Liu et al. (2017) found that personalized recommendations enhance user engagement. In the education sector, this personalization influences purchase intention by presenting users with educational options aligned with their interests and needs.

Implications for private tutorials and coaching classes

These factors have profound implications for private tutorials and coaching classes operating within C2C marketplaces and applying consumer-generated advertising:

1. **Marketing Strategies:** As per Muntinga et al, educational institutions must actively engage with user-generated content and manage their online reputation (Muntinga et al., 2011). In case of private tutorials and coaching classes, fostering positive reviews and addressing negative feedback are essential strategies to shape purchase intention.
2. **Quality Enhancement:** To boost purchase intention, private tutorials and coaching classes should prioritize the quality of their educational offerings. User-generated content serves as a feedback mechanism, offering insights into areas that need improvement (Huang et al., 2017).
3. **Community Building:** Encouraging community engagement within C2C platforms can amplify the effects of peer influence and social proof. As per earlier research, entities can nurture communities where learners share experiences and positively impact each other's purchase intentions (Muniz & O'Guinn, 2001).
4. **Partnerships and Influencer Marketing:** Collaboration with influential users within online C2C platforms can increase visibility and credibility (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). These partnerships can significantly affect purchase intention, especially when influential figures endorse educational offerings.
5. **Data Utilization:** Harnessing data analytics (Provost & Fawcett, 2013) is crucial for educational entities. In case of private tutorials and coaching classes, data can provide insights into user behaviour and preferences,

enabling them to optimize their marketing strategies and tailor recommendations.

C. Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are summarized below:

1. To test whether the perceived ‘usefulness’ of online CGA in C2C marketplace positively influences ‘purchase intention’ in education sector in the context of private tutors and coaching classes
2. To test whether the perceived ‘trustworthiness’ of online CGA in C2C marketplace positively influences ‘purchase intention’ in education sector in the context of private tutors and coaching classes
3. To identify the type of Sentiment of the private tutors and coaching centres in the unorganized education sector

D. Methodology

Research Methodology of the Qualitative Study

In the education sector, to analyze the role of online consumer-generated advertising (CGA) in Customer to Customer (C2C) marketplace to influence purchase intention, a structured methodology and design for the study was adopted. To capture the diverse perspective of online CGA, in-depth interviews were taken from 15 private tutors and trainers from different areas of study. The responses obtained were analyzed with NVivo 12 and Python 3.11.0.

NVivo software was utilized for Thematic Analysis, Word-Frequency Analysis, Word-Cloud Analysis and Cluster Analysis of Responses. Python software was utilized for Sentiment Analysis of the responses.

Market Response from In-depth Interviews

The study identified important factors influencing purchase intention of consumers. Statements associated to research theme were identified from gathered data. 15 responses are as follows:

Education sector engage consumers in different ways. Private tutorials have been an integral part of education system. In many cases, teachers do not like to institutionalize and establish coaching centres, rather they prefer to run private tutorials, and not to share their teaching tactics with others on social media. At the same time, teachers interested to institutionalize their teaching and establish coaching centres, start promotions on social media mostly without paying any cost.

Offline promotions are till now reference majorly in form of word of mouth. Some of the school teachers who engage into private tuition of students of other schools already have a good name and high references. Some of the tutors start teach in organized coaching class and once they build a good set of students, they start their own private tuition.

Word of mouth works best and considered to work best with high credibility to pull new students to the coaching class of private tutors. Many teachers invest special focus on a few brilliant students and highlight their success as success of the coaching centres. Outdoor advertising in form of distribution of pamphlets, sticking posters on walls near school gates and roads are important mode of communication too.

Earlier private tutors used to put classifieds advertisement on newspaper. A few of them started putting display classifieds advertisement containing their photographs and signatures, and thus to build an image in consumer's mind. This form of advertisement went highly successful. Before pandemic, classifieds advertisements have been one of the major tools to bring new students to the coaching class. Leading newspapers including Anandabazar Patrika used to run a classified section named '*Shikshak-Shikshika*'.

Nowadays there are aggregators and lead providers along with other paid medium to promote organized tuition courses. The organized coaching centres either employ teachers based on their CV and marksheets and run their class, or coordinate for individual tuition, and take some charge for that.

Nowadays, especially in post pandemic era, social media plays an important role in form of promotional tool or service delivery device. The display classifieds advertisements of earlier times have been promoted online on social media. Facebook including groups and LIVE sessions, WhatsApp, Telegram, LinkedIn and YouTube have been major platforms to promote courses by the unorganized tuition sector, where they do the promotion without cost. LIVE sessions are arranged in-between to make to more interactive.

Facebook advertisement in form of posting a banner with teacher's name, subject, class, timing is very popular in small towns. Facebook communities are very important mode of communication there e.g. '*Amra Krishnanagar Basi*', '*Amra Dhubulia Basi*', '*Amra Behala Basi*' etc. Communication in form of consumer-generated advertisement play very important role here with good response. In these groups teachers ask for students, guardians also ask for suitable teachers for their child. Facebook promotes these groups to join, as well as, they send notification on posts to the group members. Thus, CGA gets effective response through these groups.

School mothers' WhatsApp groups can also promote private tutors. The CGA drafted by them is promoted by mothers for their convenience.

Creating WhatsApp groups require phone numbers of target group. Facebook does not require phone numbers and the reach is also vast. But CGA should be supported by recommendations to make it effective. Positive comments on CGA carried on facebook page help generating new students or consumers. But, at the same time, since it is an open platform, negative comment might impact enrollment of new students.

There are several '*para* groups' and 'friends groups' on WhatsApp and facebook where the teacher promotes himself or herself and highlights study classes, subjects, timing etc. Guardians also find our suitable teacher for their children through such groups.

Secondary and Higher Secondary tuition providers promote their classes on facebook especially through some community groups e.g. having members from a town or locality. Sometimes open their YouTube channels and give suggestions and discuss important chapter or Question-Answer on their channel including Maths solutions. Once their number of followers increases, they promote course details and ask to join. Thus, they generate pool of new students through CGA.

Stock market training is professional training. Trainers do some certification course and highlight that. Many times they promote on facebook and other social media inviting to like their pages. Telegram group is very popular nowadays among stock market training providers as it has less restrictions and more liberty to add more number of people than WhatsApp. The stock market coaching providers open YouTube Channels and Telegram group. There they provide next day stock recommendation slightly indirectly, along with stock of the week, stock of the month, market situation, technical analysis of the stocks, fundamental analysis of the stock etc. The stock recommendations are provided by the training providers in such a way that some recommendation definitely work. Then the training provider reminds his group members on the success of his recommendation. Thus, trainer's number of followers increases. Once, the trainer gains a certain number of follower YouTube channel and Telegram, trainer starts promoting his/her course asking to join his course and learn the stock market tricks and apply the same effectively. The entire advertising communication through CGA is done without spending any money. Here coaching is not continuous but done in parts for 10 days, 1 month, 3 months etc. Some of the courses are customizes as per requirement, some are crush courses running multiple number of courses in a year, some are readymade video courses with query facility for a certain time.

Civil Service coaching providers also provide important information on current affairs on YouTube or other social media, e.g. a 5 mins analysis video on some important issue on which information is not readily available on media. They ask to subscribe their YouTube channel to stay updated. After some days, once their number of followers increases, they promote their courses through social media channels.

Study mode of instruction of the tuition classes could be offline or online. Trend for online classes increased post-pandemic. Online classes are without geographical boundaries, convenient, time saver, do not require travel time cost and energy. At the same time, sometimes online classes are costly compared to offline classes. These classes require support systems e.g. equipment like laptop or tab or smartphone, high speed internet etc. Therefore, environment plays important role here, especially what peer group is doing. Many a times, for offline classes also study materials are delivered on WhatsApp.

In many cases, whosoever is interested to study, can manage online. In case students require push to study, require offline classes.

E. Results & Findings

Respondent	Comments	Sentiment
P1	Education sector engages consumers in different ways. Private tutorials have been an integral part of the education system. In many cases, teachers do not like to institutionalize and establish coaching centres, rather they prefer to run private tutorials, and not to share their teaching tactics with others on social media. At the same time, teachers interested in institutionalizing their teaching and establish coaching centres, start promotions on social media mostly without paying any cost.	Positive
P2	Offline promotions are till now reference majorly in form of word of mouth. Some of the school teachers who engage into private tuition of students of other schools already have a good name and high references. Some of the tutors start teach in organized coaching class and once they build a good set of students, they start their own private tuition.	Positive

P3	Word of mouth works best and considered to work best with high credibility to pull new students to the coaching class of private tutors. Many teachers invest special focus on a few brilliant students and highlight their success as success of the coaching centres. Outdoor advertising in form of distribution of pamphlets, sticking posters on walls near school gates and roads are important mode of communication too.	Positive
P4	Earlier private tutors used to put classifieds advertisement on newspaper. A few of them started putting display classifieds advertisement containing their photographs and signatures, and thus to build an image in consumer's mind. This form of advertisement went highly successful. Before pandemic, classifieds advertisements have been one of the major tools to bring new students to the coaching class. Leading newspapers including Anandabazar Patrika used to run a classified section named ' <i>Shikshak-Shikshika</i> '.	Positive
P5	Nowadays there are aggregators and lead providers along with other paid medium to promote organized tuition courses. The organized coaching centres either employ teachers based on their CV and marksheets and run their class, or coordinate for individual tuition, and take some charge for that.	Negative
P6	Nowadays, especially in post pandemic era, social media plays an important role in form of promotional tool or service delivery device. The display classifieds advertisements of earlier times have been promoted online on social media. Facebook including groups and LIVE sessions, WhatsApp, Telegram, LinkedIn and YouTube have been major platforms to promote courses by the unorganized tuition sector, where they do the promotion without cost. LIVE sessions are arranged in-between to make to more interactive.	Positive
P7	Facebook advertisement in form of posting a banner with teacher's name, subject, class, timing is very popular in small towns. Facebook	Positive

	<p>communities are very important mode of communication there e.g. ‘<i>Amra Krishnanagar Basi</i>’, ‘<i>Amra Dhubulia Basi</i>’, ‘<i>Amra Behala Basi</i>’ etc. Communication in form of consumer-generated advertisement play very important role here with good response. In these groups teachers ask for students, guardians also ask for suitable teachers for their child. Facebook promotes these groups to join, as well as, they send notification on posts to the group members. Thus, CGA gets effective response through these groups.</p>	
P8	<p>School mothers’ WhatsApp groups can also promote private tutors. The CGA drafted by them is promoted by mothers for their convenience.</p>	Neutral
P9	<p>Creating WhatsApp groups require phone numbers of target group. Facebook does not require phone numbers and the reach is also vast. But CGA should be supported by recommendations to make it effective. Positive comments on CGA carried on facebook page help generating new students or consumers. But, at the same time, since it is an open platform, negative comment might impact enrollment of new students.</p>	Positive
P10	<p>There are several ‘<i>para</i> groups’ and ‘friends groups’ on WhatsApp and facebook where the teacher promotes himself or herself and highlights study classes, subjects, timing etc. Guardians also find our suitable teacher for their children through such groups.</p>	Positive
P11	<p>Secondary and Higher Secondary tuition providers promote their classes on facebook especially through some community groups e.g. having members from a town or locality. Sometimes open their YouTube channels and give suggestions and discuss important chapter or Question-Answer on their channel including Maths solutions. Once their number of followers increases, they promote course details and ask to join. Thus, they generate pool of new students through CGA.</p>	Positive

P12	<p>Stock market training is professional training. Trainers do some certification course and highlight that. Many times they promote on facebook and other social media inviting to like their pages. Telegram group is very popular nowadays among stock market training providers as it has less restrictions and more liberty to add more number of people than WhatsApp. The stock market coaching providers open YouTube Channels and Telegram group. There they provide next day stock recommendation slightly indirectly, along with stock of the week, stock of the month, market situation, technical analysis of the stocks, fundamental analysis of the stock etc. The stock recommendations are provided by the training providers in such a way that some recommendation definitely work. Then the training provider reminds his group members on the success of his recommendation. Thus, trainer's number of followers increases. Once, the trainer gains a certain number of follower YouTube channel and Telegram, trainer starts promoting his/her course asking to join his course and learn the stock market tricks and apply the same effectively. The entire advertising communication through CGA is done without spending any money. Here coaching is not continuous but done in parts for 10 days, 1 month, 3 months etc. Some of the courses are customizes as per requirement, some are crush courses running multiple number of courses in a year, some are readymade video courses with query facility for a certain time.</p>	Positive
P13	<p>Civil Service coaching providers also provide important information on current affairs on YouTube or other social media, e.g. a 5 mins analysis video on some important issue on which information is not readily available on media. They ask to subscribe their YouTube channel to stay updated. After some days, once their number of followers increases, they promote their courses</p>	Positive

	through social media channels.	
P14	Study mode of instruction of the tuition classes could be offline or online. Trend for online classes increased post pandemic. Online classes are without geographical boundary, convenient, time saver, do not require travel time cost and energy. At the same time, sometimes online classes are costly compared to offline classes. These classes require support systems e.g. equipment like laptop or tab or smartphone, high speed internet etc. Therefore, environment plays important role here, especially what peer group is doing. Many a times, for offline classes also study materials are delivered on WhatsApp.	Positive
P15	In many cases, whosoever is interested to study, can manage online. In case students require push to study, require offline classes.	Positive

Table 1: Sentiment Analysis with the responses of participants

Figure 1: Summary of Sentiment Analysis

In NVivo, autocoded themes are automatically generated by the software based on patterns and keywords found within qualitative data. These themes help researchers identify and organize content in their dataset without manually coding each individual piece of text. Autocoding is a valuable feature in NVivo for initial data exploration and hypothesis generation. Here's how autocoded themes are obtained in NVivo:

Data Import: We start by importing our qualitative data into NVivo. This data can be in the form of text documents, interviews, surveys, social media content, or any other text-based information.

Autocoding Process: NVivo uses various algorithms and natural language processing techniques to analyze the content of our data. During this process, the software identifies patterns, keywords, and phrases that appear frequently or are significant within the dataset.

Theme Generation: Based on its analysis, NVivo generates autocoded themes. These themes are essentially labels or categories that represent the common topics or subjects found in our data. NVivo assigns portions of our data to these themes based on the patterns it has detected.

Review and Refinement: While autocoded themes provide a starting point, they may not always perfectly capture the nuances of our data. Researchers typically review and refine these autocoded themes to ensure they accurately reflect the content and context of the research.

Manual Coding: After autocoding, researchers may also perform manual coding to capture additional themes or sub-themes that NVivo's algorithms may have missed. Manual coding allows for a more in-depth analysis and can capture nuances that automated methods might overlook.

Analysis and Reporting: Once the themes are established, researchers can use NVivo to analyze and explore the data further. This can involve cross-referencing themes, exploring relationships, and generating reports or visualizations to support research findings.

It is important to note that the quality and accuracy of autocoded themes in NVivo can vary depending on the complexity and nature of the data. Researchers often need to exercise judgment and domain knowledge to refine and interpret the results. Autocoded themes are useful starting points for qualitative analysis but they should be used in conjunction with manual coding and qualitative research techniques for a more comprehensive understanding of the data. The list of autocoded themes obtained from responses in this research is shown in Figure 3.

Autocoded Themes

	Name	Files
+ ☐	private tutorials	1
+ ☐	social media	1
+ ☐	coaching centres	1
+ ☐	stock market	1
+ ☐	next day stock recommendation	1
+ ☐	group	1
+ ☐	analysis	1
+ ☐	number	1
+ ☐	courses	1
+ ☐	social media channels	1
+ ☐	time	1
+ ☐	classes	1
+ ☐	offline classes	1
+ ☐	online classes	1
+ ☐	private tuition	1
+ ☐	classifieds	1
+ ☐	tuition	1
+ ☐	comments	1
+ ☐	response	2
+ ☐	teachers	2
+ ☐	groups	3

Figure 3: List of Autocoded Themes obtained from Reviews of Participants

Based on the above Thematic Analysis, another analysis which puts responses of similar types in a group is performed with the help of NVivo. The dendrogram obtained in this Cluster Analysis of 15 reviews numbered P1, P1, P3, ... , P15 is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Cluster Analysis Reviews of Participants P1, P2, P3, ..., P15

In qualitative research, dendrograms can be a valuable tool for visualizing the results of cluster analysis. Cluster analysis is a statistical technique used to group similar data points or cases together based on certain characteristics. Here is how dendrograms are used in cluster analysis in qualitative research:

Data Preparation: Before creating a dendrogram, we need to have a dataset with cases or data points that you want to cluster. In qualitative research, these cases can represent, for example, interviewees, survey respondents, or textual documents.

Similarity Measurement: In cluster analysis, we need a measure of similarity or dissimilarity between cases. For qualitative data, this often involves defining criteria for similarity based on the content or attributes of the data. Common

similarity measures include cosine similarity for text data or Jaccard similarity for categorical data.

Hierarchical Clustering: Dendrograms are typically used in hierarchical clustering, which is a method that builds a hierarchy of clusters. There are two main types of hierarchical clustering: agglomerative (bottom-up) and divisive (top-down). In agglomerative clustering, each data point starts as its own cluster, and similar clusters are merged iteratively until all data points belong to a single cluster. Divisive clustering works in the opposite direction, starting with all data points in one cluster and then dividing them into smaller clusters.

Dendrogram Construction: As the clustering algorithm progresses, it creates a dendrogram. A dendrogram is a tree-like diagram that illustrates the hierarchy of clusters. The leaves of the dendrogram represent individual data points, and branches show how clusters are merged or split at each step of the algorithm. The height or length of the branches can represent the dissimilarity between clusters or data points.

Interpretation: Dendrograms are useful for understanding the structure of our data. Researchers can interpret the dendrogram to identify natural groupings or clusters of cases. These clusters may reveal patterns, themes, or relationships within the data that were not apparent before the analysis.

Qualitative Analysis: Once clusters are defined, researchers can perform qualitative analysis within and across clusters. This may involve examining the content of interviews or documents within each cluster to identify common themes, trends, or patterns. It can also involve comparing the characteristics of clusters to draw qualitative insights.

Reporting: The findings from cluster analysis and dendrogram interpretation should be reported in our qualitative research. Researchers should provide explanations for why certain cases were grouped and what insights the clusters provide regarding the research question or objectives.

In summary, dendrograms play a role in cluster analysis by providing a visual representation of the hierarchical structure of clusters in qualitative data. They help researchers identify meaningful groupings and patterns within the data, which can lead to deeper qualitative insights and more informed research conclusions.

F. Discussions and Managerial Implications

Social media is now a significant instrument for marketing and service delivery, especially in the post-pandemic environment. On social media, the display classified ads from prior eras have received promotion. The unorganized tuition

sector has used Facebook, including groups and LIVE sessions, WhatsApp, Telegram, LinkedIn, and YouTube as important channels to advertise courses. These platforms are free to use. To make the content more participatory, LIVE sessions are scheduled in between. The market study and analysis of response highlights importance, dependency, trustworthiness and usefulness of Consumer-Generated Advertisement (CGA) in C2C marketplace in context of education sector, especially in private tuition and coaching classes, playing significant role in generating purchase intention of consumers and create pool of new students and course takers.

In the present study the researchers have obtained some prominent clusters of respondents which are as follows: (P2, P3), (P6,P13), (P14,15), (P7,P10), (P8,P9). Moreover we can form larger clusters of (P1,P2,P3,P4,P5), (P7,P8,P9,P10,P11), (P6,P12,P13,P14,P15) etc.

The results obtained from Sentiment Analysis seems quite impressive with massive percentage of positive reviews of Sentiments. So, the existing success of private tutors and coaching centres seems to last long and may attain excellence in future days. Therefore, CGAs that are viewed as being more 'useful' and 'trustworthy' encourage 'purchase intention' of the consumer. All three research proposition are thus supported by the qualitative investigation.

Since CGA in the C2C marketplace operates in close-knit communities or peer groups, the consumer feedback is immediate and transparent, making it trustworthy and useful for future consumers. In case of corporate advertising, there may be a discrepancy between consumer feedback and actual deliverables because the company pays its marketing and branding teams, social media influencers, and present consumers to provide positive reviews.

The usage of the findings of the study is where the work's uniqueness lies. CGAs that are perceived as more 'useful' and 'trustworthy' shall boost the consumer's 'buying intention'. Therefore, CGA influencing high purchase intention would be highly instrumental in generating a relevant potential consumer database created from the feedback window post LIVE sessions, feedback form, or registration of new course takers. The database would contain information including name, age, contact information, mail id etc. Thus, CGA would have a significant impact on producing a continuous flow of both present and potential customers. This database can be nurtured with a variety of marketing techniques, such as email marketing, SMS blasts, WhatsApp campaigns, follow-ups call and finally some of the potential consumers are converted to course takers. Additionally, consumer feedback aids in the enhancement of course quality.

The novelty of this study lies in the new direction it gives to managerial practices. With the structural shift of the industry especially post-pandemic,

greater performance in the changing market trend will result from an appreciation of and comprehension of the influencing factors- perceived usefulness and perceived trustworthiness. Thus CGA, the new avatar of online marketing in the service sector has high managerial implications, consumer implications, and overall marketing implications, adding to the study's unique contribution.

G. Conclusion and Scope of Further Research

Private tutoring and coaching businesses' current performance seems to last a long time and may reach excellence in the future. As a result, CGAs that are perceived as more "useful" and "trustworthy" stimulate "purchase intention" from the consumer. Thus, the qualitative inquiry supports all three of the research hypotheses.

The Grounded Theory methodology provides a robust foundation for ongoing exploration and inquiry. Its adaptable nature allows for continuous investigation without rigid constraints. Researchers can further delve into the depth and complexity of phenomena, refining existing theories or uncovering new ones. Grounded Theory's iterative and inductive approach fosters a dynamic cycle of data collection, coding, and theory development, ensuring that the research process remains open-ended and responsive to emerging insights. This continuous exploration serves as an enduring framework for deepening our understanding of various subjects across disciplines.

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